

Title: 17q12-q21 variants interact with early-life exposures to modify asthma risk in Black children

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Methods

Study design and participants

URECA is a longitudinal birth cohort study of high-risk children¹ who were recruited from urban census tracts in Baltimore, Boston, New York City, and St. Louis, in which >20% of the residents were living below the poverty line. Pregnant women aged 18 years or older were asked to participate if they lived in one of these areas. Children were included if they were born at or after 34 weeks of gestation, and had at least one biologic parent with a history of asthma, allergic rhinitis, or atopic dermatitis. Between February 2005 and March 2007, 560 children were enrolled in URECA and were followed to age 10 years, of which 442 (79%) had outcome data to classify asthma status at age 7. Of these, 318 (72%) were self-reported as Black by a parent or guardian and were included in this study. Black race was determined if the participant indicated that they were “Black,” “African American/Black American,” or “Other Black.”

Data collection

The measured environmental exposures included in our study were indoor allergen concentration in house dust, house dust microbiota data, and the number of colds in the first three years of life (Figure E4). Home environmental data were collected during home visits at 3 months after birth, and in the second and third years of life. House dust samples were assayed for common indoor allergens, including Bla g 1 (cockroach), Can f 1 (dog), Fel d 1 (cat), Der f 1 and Der p 1 (house dust mites), and Mus m 1 (mouse), using an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA; Indoor Biotechnologies, Charlottesville, Va). A sum of exposure index was derived by combining cat, mouse, cockroach, and dog allergen, the four allergens that were significantly or nearly significantly associated with the development of asthma, into a single index based on quartiles of exposure to individual allergens, resulting in an index with a range of 0 to 12 (sum of quartiles 0, 1, 2 or 3 with 0 being the lowest and 3 being the highest level of exposure). The sum of exposure index at 3 months, and the cumulative sum of exposure index at 3 months, 2 years, and 3 years of age, were used as separate exposure indices. Missing data for the sum of exposure index was imputed using imputation by chained equations. In this study, we used the average of the 8 imputations to perform the association and gene-exposure interaction analyses. The number of colds was captured through post-natal questionnaires that were administered to a parent or guardian every 3 months; year 1 and cumulative sum of colds consist of the sum of the number of colds that were reported during the first year or the first three years of life respectively. House dust microbiota data was obtained from house dust samples collected at 3-months of age. The dust specimens underwent culture-independent microbial profiling using 16S rRNA sequencing. We used Faith's phylogenetic diversity in our analyses to capture the richness

and diversity of the house dust microbiota. Please refer to O'Connor *et al.* for detailed methods on data collection.²

Primary outcome

The prespecified primary outcome of our study was the diagnosis of asthma at age 7 years. Asthma was defined at the year 7 visit as meeting at least one of the following 3 criteria: (1) a parent-reported physician's diagnosis of asthma between age 4 and 7 years combined with asthma symptoms or the use of asthma controlled medication for 6 of the past 12 months; (2) a methacholine challenge PC20 value of 5mg/mL or less or albuterol-induced FEV1 reversibility of 10% or more, in addition to asthma symptoms or use of asthma controller medication for 6 of the past 12 months; or (3) report in the past 12 months of 2 or more wheezing episodes, 2 or more doctor's office visits for asthma/wheeze, 1 or more hospitalizations for asthma/wheeze, or use of controller medications for 6 of the past 12 months. Children who did not meet any of these criteria were considered as not having asthma at age 7.

Genotype of the 17q12-q21 variants

Nine single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) from the 17q12-q21 locus were selected based on linkage disequilibrium (LD) patterns and previous associations with childhood-onset asthma and gene expression: rs2941504, rs2517955, rs12936231, rs2305480, rs7216389, rs4065275, rs8076131, rs8069202, rs3859192, as described in Ober *et al.*³ Genotyping was performed using a TaqMan® assay (Applied Biosystems, Foster, CA). Genotypes were available for 313 of 318 Black URECA children. Genotyping success rate was >99% and all SNPs were in Hardy-Weinberg

equilibrium ($p > 0.005$). Of the 313 children with genotypes, 263 also had ancestry PCs available from previous genotyping studies (see description below). One child from a sibling pair was removed from the analysis resulting in a final sample size of 262. Due to allele frequencies and the small sample size, genotypes with < 10 counts in a group (SNP x exposure variable) were combined. This was required for 6 out of the 9 SNPs: rs2517955 (TT+TC/CC), rs2305480 (AA+AG/GG), rs7216389 (CC+CT/TT), rs8076131 (GG+GA/AA), rs8069202 (GG/GA+AA), rs3859192 (CC/CT+TT). Genotype grouping was applied across all exposures. An LD (r^2) plot was drawn using Haploview v4.2⁴ and the genotype data from the subjects in this study.

Association and interaction studies

Association tests with asthma were performed using a logistic regression and linear regression with gene expression (eQTLs). Covariates included sex, the URECA study site, and the first 3 ancestry principal components (PCs). Ancestry PCs were calculated on a set of 3,534 SNPs that were genotyped in 481 URECA samples, accounting for subject relatedness, using PC-Air⁵ and PC-Relate.⁶ To test for interactions between 17q12-q21 SNPs and early-life exposures on asthma, we included an interaction term for the exposure x genotype. Sum of colds and sum of exposure index were each log-transformed prior to the analyses. Note that all log transformations are natural log based. As many values were equal to 0, 1 was added to each sum of exposure or sum of colds before the transformation. To correct for multiple testing, a Bonferroni correction was applied for each analysis based on the number of tests performed.

Analysis of gene expression and eQTLs

RNA sequencing was available from nasal epithelial cells (NECs) of 189 Black URECA children collected at 11 years old, as described previously.³ We performed expression quantitative trait loci (eQTL) mapping for the 3 SNPs that showed suggestive interactions, rs7216389, rs8069202, and rs3859192, using the same model as in Ober *et al.*³ Briefly, genes with <1 count per million (CPM) in >25% of the samples were removed and normalization of the remaining genes was done using log-transformed CPM. We included the 8 genes at 17q12-q21 that were expressed in tissue: *PGAP3*, *ERBB2*, *MIEN1*, *IKZF3*, *GSDMB*, *ORMDL3*, *GSDMA*, and *GRB7* in NECs only. We used FastQTL⁷ and eQTLs with p-value < 0.0021 (Bonferroni adjusted for 24 tests) were considered significant. We included as covariates sex, URECA study site, the first 3 ancestry PCs, sequencing batch, epithelial cell proportion, and 7 latent factors to correct for unwanted variations.⁸

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Table E1. Associations (main effects) between early-life exposures and asthma at age 7 in Black children of the URECA cohort

Exposures		N sample ¹	OR (95% CI)	Pval
Sum of exposure index ² +1 (log transformed)	Cumulative ³	262	0.59 (0.35-0.99)	0.048
	3 months	262	0.53 (0.32-0.88)	0.015
Sum of colds +1 (log transformed)	Cumulative ⁴	262	3.51 (1.87-6.57)	8.68x10⁻⁵
	1 year	262	2.03 (1.24-3.33)	0.0052
Microbiota diversity	Phylogenetic diversity	134	1.00 (0.99-1.01)	0.49

¹number of samples that pass QC for genotyping data out of 262, ²Sum of exposures is calculated by combining cat, mouse, cockroach, and dog allergen concentration into a single index based on quartiles of exposure to individual allergens (0 for lowest quartile, 3 for highest quartile) resulting in a range from 0 to 12. For more details, see O'Connor *et al.* A unit (+1) was added to the sum of quartiles prior to log transformation to compensate for the presence of 0. Odds ratios are from a logistic regression model controlling for sex, study site and 3 first ancestry Principal Components, averaged across 8 imputed data sets and represent the odds for an interquartile increase in exposure +1 (log transformed), ³Cumulative exposure is the sum of allergen concentration at 3 months, 2 years and 3 years. ⁴Cumulative sum of colds are the sum of colds that occurred from years 0-3 years. OR = Odds ratio, CI = confidence interval. Bonferroni p-value cutoff = 0.05/5 = 0.01.

Table E2. Association between nine 17q12-q21 single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) and asthma at age 7 in Black children of the URECA cohort

SNP	Gene	Alleles ¹	N samp ²	EAF	OR (95% CI)	Pval
rs2941504	<i>PGAP3</i>	G/A	260	0.46	1.05 (0.71-1.56)	0.79
rs2517955	<i>PGAP3</i>	T/C	259	0.80	1.91 (1.17-3.12)	0.010
rs12936231	<i>ZPBP2</i>	G/C	259	0.48	1.15 (0.78-1.69)	0.48
rs2305480	<i>GSDMB</i>	A/G	260	0.90	1.88 (0.94-3.76)	0.074
rs7216389	<i>GSDMB</i>	C/T	260	0.82	1.27 (0.77-2.10)	0.35
rs4065275	<i>ORMDL3</i>	A/G	260	0.62	1.01 (0.67- 1.49)	0.95
rs8076131	<i>ORMDL3</i>	G/A	258	0.85	1.53 (0.88-2.66)	0.14
rs8069202	<i>GSDMA</i>	G/A	260	0.33	0.83 (0.54-1.27)	0.38
rs3859192	<i>GSDMA</i>	C/T	259	0.36	0.77 (0.52-1.15)	0.20

¹ effect allele in bold, ²number of samples that pass QC for genotyping data out of 262, EAF= effect allele frequency, the effect allele was defined as asthma risk allele in Europeans;⁹ OR= Odds ratio, CI = confidence interval. Bonferroni p-value cutoff = $0.05/9 = 0.0056$

Table E3. Gene-environment interaction between 17q12-q21 SNPs and early-life exposures on asthma risk at age 7 in URECA Black children

SNP ¹	Location	Exposure	Est _{SNP}	P _{SNP}	Est _{exp}	P _{exp}	Est _{int}	P _{int}
rs2941504 (GG vs GA vs AA)	<i>PGAP3</i>	Sum exp ind (cumul) ^{2,3}	0.35	0.66	-0.43	0.29	-0.14	0.69
		Sum exp ind (3 mo)	0.17	0.73	-0.51	0.23	-0.14	0.69
		Sum colds 1-3y ⁴	-1.49	0.26	0.75	0.14	0.61	0.23
		Sum colds 1y	-1.15	0.11	0.077	0.86	0.74	0.073
		Phylogenetic diversity ⁵	1.85	0.53	0.005	0.77	-0.008	0.61
rs2517955 (TT/TC vs CC)	<i>PGAP3</i>	Sum exp ind (cumul)	1.85	0.14	0.24	0.80	-0.46	0.39
		Sum exp ind (3 mo)	2.04	0.019	0.99	0.35	-0.91	0.11
		Sum colds 1-3y	0.98	0.59	1.38	0.24	-0.054	0.94
		Sum colds 1y	0.90	0.34	0.80	0.41	-0.06	0.91
		Phylogenetic diversity	1.54	0.41	0.0012	0.94	-0.002	0.79
rs12936231 (GG vs GC vs CC)	<i>ZBP2</i>	Sum exp ind (cumul)	0.25	0.76	-0.44	0.30	-0.11	0.77
		Sum exp ind (3 mo)	-0.028	0.95	-0.66	0.12	0.020	0.95
		Sum colds 1-3y	-1.49	0.23	0.71	0.17	0.61	0.20
		Sum colds 1y	-0.95	0.16	0.13	0.76	0.62	0.12
		Phylogenetic diversity	-0.37	0.78	-0.007	0.43	0.005	0.51
rs2305480 (AA/AG vs GG)	<i>GSDMB</i>	Sum exp ind (cumul)	-0.18	0.74	-0.12	0.70	-0.49	0.45
		Sum exp ind (3 mo)	-0.33	0.71	-0.70	0.49	-0.60	0.40
		Sum colds 1-3y	0.58	0.81	2.76	0.10	0.46	0.57
		Sum colds 1y	-0.83	0.41	0.078	0.94	0.63	0.37
		Phylogenetic diversity	-1.00	0.61	-0.014	0.40	0.003	0.80
rs7216389 (CC/CT vs TT)	<i>GSDMB</i>	Sum exp ind (cumul)	2.51	0.056	1.40	0.16	-1.14	0.038
		Sum exp ind (3 mo)	1.25	0.13	1.02	0.29	-0.98	0.067
		Sum colds 1-3y	-2.39	0.16	-0.31	0.77	0.96	0.15
		Sum colds 1y	-0.57	0.52	0.07	0.94	0.39	0.45
		Phylogenetic diversity	-3.50	0.096	-0.033	0.079	0.018	0.098
rs4065275 (AA vs AG vs GG)	<i>ORMDL3</i>	Sum exp ind (cumul)	-0.18	0.84	-0.61	0.32	0.027	0.95
		Sum exp ind (3 mo)	-0.17	0.75	-0.72	0.21	0.051	0.89
		Sum colds 1-3y	-2.09	0.061	0.34	0.54	0.80	0.066
		Sum colds 1y	-1.11	0.077	-0.10	0.84	0.68	0.069
		Phylogenetic diversity ⁵	-1.75	0.35	-0.016	0.26	0.009	0.34

rs8076131 (GG/GA vs AA)	ORMDL3	Sum exp ind (cumul)	2.41	0.10	1.23	0.27	-0.98	0.099
		Sum exp ind (3 mo)	1.73	0.076	1.40	0.21	-1.14	0.059
		Sum colds 1-3y	-1.44	0.44	0.084	0.95	0.70	0.32
		Sum colds 1y	-0.19	0.86	0.13	0.91	0.33	0.60
		Phylogenetic diversity	-1.98	0.38	-0.025	0.23	0.013	0.26
rs8069202 (GG vs GA/AA)	GSDMA	Sum exp ind (cumul)	1.42	0.19	0.57	0.42	-0.79	0.094
		Sum exp ind (3 mo)	0.49	0.47	0.31	0.68	-0.65	0.17
		Sum colds 1-3y	-4.25	0.014	-0.95	0.33	1.53	0.021
		Sum colds 1y	-2.58	0.0047	-1.43	0.08	1.41	0.0082
		Phylogenetic diversity	-2.95	0.13	-0.32	0.076	0.017	0.094
rs3859192 (CC vs CT/TT)	GSDMA	Sum exp ind (cumul)	1.32	0.21	0.51	0.48	-0.73	0.12
		Sum exp ind (3 mo)	0.79	0.25	0.63	0.41	-0.84	0.078
		Sum colds 1-3y	-4.72	0.0068	-1.28	0.19	1.74	0.0093
		Sum colds 1y	-2.43	0.0070	-1.42	0.088	1.37	0.0099
		Phylogenetic diversity	-2.64	0.18	-0.032	0.093	0.016	0.11

Bonferroni p-value cutoff = $0.05/(5*9) = 0.0011$. ¹Effect allele in bold. ²Sum of exposure index is calculated by combining cat, mouse, cockroach, and dog into a single index based on quartiles of exposure to individual allergens (0 for lowest quartile, 3 for highest quartile) resulting in a range from 0 to 12. ³Cumulative exposure is defined as the sum of allergen concentrations at age 3 months, 2 years, and 3 years. ⁴Cumulative sum of colds are the sum of colds that occurred from years 0-3. ⁵ The smaller samples size = combined phenotypes for rs2941504 (GG/GA vs AA) and rs4065275 (AA/AG vs GG).

Figure E1. Relationship between asthma at age 7 the cumulative allergen exposure index in Black children in the URECA cohort (left panel), stratified by genotype at r7216389 (CC+CT vs. TT) (right panel)

Figure E2. Linkage disequilibrium pattern for the nine SNPs on the 17q12-q21 locus in Black children in the URECA cohort.

Figure E3. Relationship between asthma at age 7 and sum of colds in the first three years of life in Black children in the URECA cohort (left panel), stratified by genotype at rs3859192 (CC vs. CT+TT) (middle panel), and stratified by genotype at rs8069292 (GG vs. GA+AA) (right panel).

Figure E4. Distribution of exposures within Black children of the URECA cohort, prior to log transformation